

PHILIPPINE INFORMAL READING INVENTORY (PHIL-IRI) PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF BATANGAS CITY

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ABSTRACT

It is an accepted phenomenon that reading is a relevant part in the development of an individual's whole being and is one of the indicators that a person is literate. Along this concern, this study aimed to analyze the Phil-IRI results during school year 2018-2019 to describe the reading performance level of the students. It also aimed to identify the evidence of support to reading enhancement activities in terms of role of administrators, teachers and stakeholders. Moreover, the constraints encountered by the teachers in the application of the dimensions of reading comprehension were also determined. It also found ways to identify the reading enhancement activities that can be prepared to improve further the students' reading comprehension skills. The study made use of the descriptive type of research with a researcher-made questionnaire as the main instrument in gathering data. In addition, documentary analysis of the results of Phil-IRI was also done to substantiate the data gathered from the questionnaire. The results revealed that the reading performance of the students was on instructional level. Moreover, administrators, teachers and other stakeholders greatly supported the reading comprehension enhancement activities. Comparison of teachers' and administrators' responses revealed no significant differences with regard to the readiness of the schools in enhancing students' comprehension skills and on evidence of support to reading comprehension enhancement activities. Findings also indicated that the problems confronted by the teachers were poor study habits and insufficient knowledge on vocabulary. Reading activities were prepared to enhance the performance of the students.

Keywords:(a) *Education and Teaching Reading*; (b) *Philippine Informal Reading Inventory*, *Reading Comprehension*, (c) *Descriptive Method*; (d) *Philippines*